

Student Learning Achievement: The Role of Learning Motivation and Online Learning

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ABSTRACT: The Covid-19 pandemic has disrupted the conventional learning process. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of learning motivation and online learning media on student achievement in the Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Warmadewa. This survey was conducted on 55 students randomly. Test the hypothesis in this study using SEM-PLS analysis with the help of SmartPLS 3.0 software. Research result shows 1) learning motivation has a positive and significant effect on student learning achievement, which means an increase in learning motivation will be followed by an increase in student learning achievement. 2) Learning Media *on line* positive and significant effect on student achievement, which means that the better the online learning media, the student's learning achievement will increase. This research illustrates that for the head of the Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Warmadewa, if you want to improve student achievement, you should pay attention to increasing motivation and online learning media. Exploring in-depth information about students' learning motivation and online learning media to succeed in participating in the recovery of the Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Warmadewa.

KEYWORDS: Motivation, online learning media, learning achievement

I. INTRODUCTION

The impact of the Covid-19 pandemic, which is now starting to penetrate the world, has forced the government to close all educational institutions. In addition, the government also limits human activities outside the home in an effort to limit interactions between many people, which aims to break the chain of the spread of Covid-19. This policy does not only apply in Indonesia, but also in countries that have been exposed to Covid-19. With this policy, the campus implements teaching and learning activities from a distance or online learning (in a network). Implementation of the distance learning process in the era of the Covid-19 pandemic, lecturers are required to choose and use the right method so that the teaching and learning process continues, in other words, educational interactions are created.

Based on the observations that have been made, it turns out that there are still students who are less disciplined in terms of learning and lectures. The phenomenon of the Overnight Speed System is still the prima donna in the way students study at the Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Warmadewa, both in terms of doing assignments or facing exams whose deadline is tomorrow so that the results obtained are less than optimal. Students' perception of complicated and too difficult courses also causes students to be less motivated to learn. This causes students' interest in learning to be less and student learning achievement to be less than optimal.

From the initial study in the field, an interesting experience was obtained, the results of interviews with 5 semester VI students of the management study program, namely there were some students who did not have their own lecture notes because these students were quite satisfied with learning from photocopies of their friends' notes, there were some students who did not prepare themselves. regarding the lecture material that will be taught by the lecturer so that it seems very foreign because students have never studied it before, there are some students who do not repeat the lecture material that has been given by the lecturer as soon as possible on the grounds that there are many other opportunities to repeat the material at other times, there are some students who study before the semester exam or if there is an assignment from the lecturer that requires understanding

The results of observations made by researchers for about a month also obtained data that students' learning motivation in gaining knowledge through the learning and teaching process is still lacking, this is evidenced by when the teaching and learning process there are students who are less responsive and act indifferent, when given assignments, they always give reasons that too many assignments have been given, when given the exam grid, students are not motivated to learn but are used for material for making cheats, when practicing skills lab students are less enthusiastic about trying, when given time to be independent only a few students use it. This opportunity resulted in them getting poor test scores and many taking remedial exams.

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According to Slameto (2010), there are two factors that influence learning, namely internal factors and external factors. Internal factors include physical / physical, physical maturity, fatigue, psychology in the form of talents, interests, intelligence, motivation and cognitive abilities and achievements. External factors include the natural environment, family environment (how parents educate, relationships between family members, home atmosphere, family economic situation, understanding of parents, cultural background), school environment (teaching methods, learning media, curriculum, teacher-student relations). , student relations with students, school discipline, school time, lesson standards above the size, learning methods, homework assignments), and the community environment (student activities in the community, friends to hang out with, forms of community life). Baharuddin (2009):

The term learning achievement consists of two words, namely achievement and learning. Winkel (1996) suggests that, "Learning achievement is evidence of success that has been achieved by someone". Learning achievement is also the result of the efforts that have been made by students (students) in the process of changing behavior which is expressed in the form of understanding, mastering, using, and assessing attitudes, values, knowledge, and basic skills, as well as more satisfying skills development, after experiencing the learning process. Student learning achievement can be assessed by giving an evaluation or assignment by the lecturer. According to Slameto (2010), external factors are divided into three (3) factors, namely: family factors, school factors, and community factors. Student learning is influenced by several factors, both factors that come from within the student and factors that come from outside the student. All of these factors are very important to encourage students to improve their satisfactory learning achievement, which is better than before.

The development of information and technology is very important considering that every year or even every month, science and information is always evolving. With the era of increasingly developing technology, it is hoped that learning programs can make good use of technology. One of the online learning methods that is currently developing and starting to be used is e-learning. E learning is a special application that is used for online learning that can be done remotely, making it easier for lecturers to create, classify and divide tasks. Besides that, lecturers and students can carry out learning activities at any time through online e-learning classes and students will also be able to learn, listen, and learn at any time read and send tasks remotely.

In teaching and learning activities the role of motivation is very necessary. The low motivation of students to learn is often suspected to be the cause of the low quality of graduates of a university. This causes in some private universities, learning motivation factors get special attention. This factor raises a dilemma. Actually, it is impossible for a student to master learning materials well if the motivation to learn is low, but if passed, this has an impact on students. Previous research on the relationship between learning motivation and student achievement also showed different results. Ramdhan and Harsono (2015) show the results that the learning motivation variable has a significant influence on the learning achievement variable, which has a low degree of association. Meanwhile, Mediawati (2015) shows that student learning motivation and lecturer competence have a positive and significant influence either partially or simultaneously on student learning achievement.

In fact, especially in Indonesia or several universities with similar problems, they feel they are not ready to use learning technology with an online system or online. This is a new problem that must be solved. Several problems that arise related to the online learning system, both in the form of student readiness, mastery of technology, other obstacles experienced while using this system. So that evaluation can be done to minimize the obstacles and problems faced by students while using this method. Thus, in the future, online learning will be better and educational outcomes are achieved in accordance with the noble ideals of the Indonesian nation contained in the opening of the 4th paragraph of the 1945 Constitution, one of which is the intellectual life of the nation. The change in learning methods from classical and face-to-face methods to online methods has received various reactions from students. Short time, lots of assignments, number of quotas, signal conditions make students try to prepare everything well. In addition, it is also known that online learning programs have hidden skills, namely the ability to master technology and use it properly. On the other hand, the policy of temporary closure of educational institutions with various supporting facilities in the short and medium term has affected many students, especially those who live in areas with limited infrastructure and other supporting capacities, which further widens the digital divide. the many assignments, the number of quotas, the signal conditions make students struggle to prepare everything well. In addition, it is also known that online learning programs have hidden skills, namely the ability to master technology and use it properly. On the other hand, the policy of temporarily closing educational institutions with various supporting facilities in the short and medium term has affected many students, especially those who live in areas with limited infrastructure and other supporting capacities, which further widens the digital divide. The many assignments, the number of quotas, the signal conditions make students struggle to prepare everything well. In addition, it is also known that online learning programs have hidden skills, namely the ability to master technology and use it properly. On the other hand, the policy of temporary closure of educational institutions with various supporting facilities in the short and medium term has affected many students, especially those who live in areas with limited infrastructure and other supporting capacities, which further widens the digital divide. In

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Online or online learning (on a network) is carried out through various applications that can support the learning process starting from face-to-face applications such as zoom, google meet, and other online media platforms such as google classroom, whatsapp group, etc. The results of initial observations by lecturers of the Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Warmadewa, almost 90 percent use e learning. The use of the Google classroom application is mostly used at the Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Warmadewa by combining other applications such as whatsapp group, zoom, workplace and google meet to support the learning process .

The use of online-based learning media can affect learning outcomes, so educators must be careful in choosing and using media. In addition to using online learning media, in this pandemic situation, students also carry out an independent learning process or independent learning. Independence in learning demands a great responsibility on the participants themselves so that teaching participants try to carry out various activities to achieve learning goals. Hiemstra quoted by Darmayanti, et al (2004) states about independent learning as a form of learning that has the main responsibility for planning, implementing, and evaluating its business.

Furthermore, the challenge of online learning is the availability of internet services. Some students access the internet using cellular services, and a small number use Wifi services. When the online learning policy was implemented at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Warmadewa University, students returned home. They have difficulty cellular signal when in their respective areas, even if there is a signal that is obtained is very weak. This is a challenge in itself in the application of online learning at the Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Warmadewa. Online learning has weaknesses when internet services are weak, and lecturer instructions are poorly understood by students (Astuti, P & Febrian, F, 2019). Another challenge faced is the obstacle in financing online learning.

The results of the study also reported that not a few students had difficulties in understanding the lecture material given online. Teaching materials are usually delivered in the form of readings that are not easily understood by students thoroughly (Sadikin, A., & Hakim, N., 2019). They assume that the materials and assignments are not enough because they need a direct explanation by the lecturer. Garrison & Cleveland-Innes (2005) and Swan (2002) reported that classes where the lecturer often came in and gave explanations provided better learning than classes where the lecturers rarely came to class and gave explanations.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Achievement Motivation Theory

Achievement Motivation Theory seeks to explain and predict behavior and performance based on one's need for achievement, power, and affiliation" (Lussier & Achua, 2007). Achievement Motivation Theory is also referred to as Acquired Needs Theory or Learned Needs Theory. Daft (2008) defines Acquired Needs Theory as "McClelland's theory which proposes that certain types of needs (achievement, affiliation, power) are acquired during an individual's life". Achievement Motivation Theory evolved from McClelland's work beginning in the 1940s. In 1958 McClelland described human motives in the Methods for Measuring Human Motivation chapter of Atkinson's book *Motives in Fantasy, Action, and Society*. At that point, McClelland identified human motives related to achievement motives, affiliation motives, sexual motives, and power motives. In his later work, *The Achieving Society* (McClelland, 1961), however, McClelland focused only on the need for Achievement, the need for Affiliation, and the need for Power. In essence, McClelland's theory postulates that people are motivated to varying degrees by their need for achievement, need for power, and need for affiliation and that these needs are acquired, or learned, over an individual's lifetime (Daft, 2008; Lussier & Achua, 2007).). In other words, most people have and will exhibit a combination of the three needs. and the need for Power. In essence, McClelland's theory postulates that people are motivated to varying degrees by their need for achievement, need for power, and need for affiliation and that these needs are acquired, or learned, over the course of an individual's lifetime (Daft, 2008; Lussier & Achua, 2007).). In other words, most people have and will exhibit a combination of the three needs. and the need for Power. In essence, McClelland's theory postulates that people are motivated to varying degrees by their need for achievement, need for power, and need for affiliation and that these needs are acquired, or learned, over the course of an individual's lifetime (Daft, 2008; Lussier & Achua, 2007).). In other words, most people have and will exhibit a combination of the three needs.

Student Learning Achievement

In teaching and learning activities the role of motivation is very necessary. The low motivation of students to learn is often suspected to be the cause of the low quality of graduates of a university. This causes in some private universities, learning motivation factors get special attention. Measuring instrument of student success in following the learning process in an educational institution is indicated by student achievement.

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Purwanto (2006) suggests that learning achievement is motivated by several factors which can basically be grouped into two parts, namely factors originating from within students (internal factors) and factors originating from outside students (external factors). Factors originating from within students (internal factors) include: interest, motivation, learning methods, maturity and readiness, and so on. Meanwhile, factors originating from outside the students (external factors) include: teachers/lecturers, school environment, family, community environment, and so on.

One of the internal factors that can affect learning achievement is learning motivation. This learning motivation will encourage someone to do something so as to achieve the goal. If students are encouraged to do learning, there will be an effective learning which will ultimately result in high learning achievement. This is in line with the opinion of Sardiman AM (2006) which states that motivation can function as a driver of effort and achievement. Someone does an effort because of motivation. The existence of good motivation in learning will show good results. In other words, with diligent effort and especially aware of motivation, someone who learns will be able to give birth to good achievements. The intensity of a person's motivation will greatly determine the level of achievement of learning achievement. Teachers (read: lecturers) are one of the external factors that affect learning achievement. The teacher is a component that has a strategic role in the implementation of learning. Teachers/lecturers have a key role in every effort to improve the quality, relevance, and efficiency of education. In the hands of teachers, the quality of education can be pursued in a better direction. This forces teachers to be able to be optimally prepared for their competencies, because after all, teacher competence reflects the teacher's performance or teacher's ability to teach in the classroom so that it can be ascertained that the better the competence of the teacher, the greater the possibility that student learning achievement will also increase. Wijaya and Rusyan (1994: 1) suggests that the teacher is a very dominant and most important factor in formal education in general because for students teachers are often used as role models, even self-identification figures. Therefore, teachers should have adequate behavior and abilities to develop their students as a whole. To carry out their duties properly in accordance with their profession, teachers need to master various things as their competencies. Learning is a process of effort by a person to obtain a new behavior change as a whole, as a result of his own experience in interaction with his environment (Ircham Machfoedz, 2005). Even become a figure of self-identification. Therefore, teachers should have adequate behavior and abilities to develop their students as a whole. To carry out their duties properly in accordance with their profession, teachers need to master various things as their competencies. Learning is a process of effort by a person to obtain a new behavior change as a whole, as a result of his own experience in interaction with his environment (Ircham Machfoedz, 2005). Even become a figure of self-identification. Therefore, teachers should have adequate behavior and abilities to develop their students as a whole. To carry out their duties properly in accordance with their profession, teachers need to master various things as their competencies. Learning is a process of effort by a person to obtain a new behavior change as a whole, as a result of his own experience in interaction with his environment (Ircham Machfoedz, 2005).

From the description above, it can be concluded that learning is an attempt to acquire new things in knowledge and behavior with their own mental activities. Principles in learning According to Ircham (2005) There are several principles in learning which include: 1) Based on the requirements of learning methods 2) Based on learning facilities 3) Based on the nature of learning 4) Based on the material provided 5) Based on the technique of giving material b. Factors that influence the learning process The success or failure of learning depends on various factors, according to Purwanto (2006) there are 2 factors, namely: 1) Factors that exist in the organism itself which we call "individual factors". 2) Factors that exist outside the individual which we call "social factors".

Motivation to learn

Learning Motivation Motivation comes from the word "motive" which means as a force contained in the individual, which causes the individual to act or do. Motivation is an impulse contained in a person to try to make changes in behavior that are better in meeting their needs (Uno, 2008). Learning motivation is an impulse that moves, directs, and maintains student behavior in statistics learning activities, which arise from within or from outside the student, which is reflected in the need, effort and perseverance to achieve the best possible learning outcomes. Someone who learns with high motivation will carry out his learning activities in earnest, full of enthusiasm and passion. On the other hand, students who study with low motivation will be lazy and even do not want to do tasks related to the lesson (Dai and Sternberg, 2004). Learning Motivation The word motivation comes from the Latin movere which means "to move". According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI) that motivation is an impulse that arises in a person consciously or not to take an action with a specific purpose.

According to Robbins (2015) that "Motivation is a process that describes a person's strength, direction and persistence in an effort to achieve goals. Meanwhile, according to Griffin (2013) that motivation is a series of forces that cause people to behave in certain ways. So, motivation is an impulse that arises from a person that causes changes to achieve goals, needs and desires. If the above characteristics are owned by a student, it means that the student has a strong enough motivation to learn to participate in learning activities. According to Sri Hapsari (2005) that there are two types of motivation, namely as follows:

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- 1) Intrinsic learning motivation is a learning drive that comes from within a person without external stimulation. Intrinsic motivation is generally related to talent and intelligence factors in a person. The factors that influence intrinsic motivation are self-desire, satisfaction, good habits and awareness.
- 2) Extrinsic learning motivation is the motivation to learn that comes from outside a person. The factors that influence extrinsic motivation are enthusiasm, praise, advice, gifts, punishments and imitating something.

The results of research by Ramdhan (2015) show that the variable of learning motivation has a significant influence on the variable of learning achievement, which has a low level of relationship. This is because students have other motives for participating in the Distance Education program, one of which is the motive for career development. Meanwhile, Wijaya's research (2018) shows that the results of student learning motivation have a significant positive effect on student achievement. According to the article *Relationship of learning motivation with academic achievement* stated that there was no relationship between learning motivation and academic achievement of students of the midwifery D3 study program majoring in midwifery Poltekkes Kemenkes Gorontalo as indicated by the value of (0.62). Students are expected to pay attention to other factors to improve academic achievement besides learning motivation, including: intelligence/IQ, instrumental (curriculum, facilities/facilities), interests, talents, and learning methods (Astuti, ER, Zakaria, R, 2021). Based on the background and theoretical studies, the proposed hypothesis is as follows:

H1: Learning motivation has a positive and significant effect on student learning achievement.

Online Learning Media

Online learning media (Sofyana & Abdul, 2019) is a learning tool or intermediary that is carried out not face to face, but using a platform that can help the teaching and learning process that is carried out even though it is far away. Teaching and learning activities during the Covid-19 pandemic are carried out using a remote method with an online system (e-learning). E-learning can be defined as a digital learning process through the internet (Jethro, et al. 2012). E-learning is the use of learning media using the internet, to deliver a series of solutions that can improve knowledge and skills.

Santika (2020) in research Factors that affect Student Academic Achievement stated that (1) seat position has a significant effect on academic achievement. (2) Learning facilities have no significant effect on academic achievement. (3) Achievement motivation has an effect on academic achievement. (4) There is a joint effect of independent variables on academic achievement. Aurora A, Efendi, H (2019) The effect of using e-learning media on student learning motivation at the Electrical Engineering Education Study Program (PSPTE) Padang State University, the regression coefficient (x) is 0.737. This value means that for every 1% addition of the value of using e-learning media, the value of student motivation increases by 0.737. While the results of Sudibjo's research (2015) stated that student learning outcomes after using Google classroom at SMPN 4 Surabaya increased, namely the average pre-test result was 39.76 and when learning using science learning media with e-learning based on Google classroom, the cognitive value of students is quite increased compared to before to 76.05. Rahayu and Sutarsih (2020) state that there is a significant relationship between the use of Google classroom and student learning outcomes. It can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between the use of Google classroom and student learning outcomes.

Based on the background and theoretical studies, the proposed hypothesis is as follows:

H2: Online Learning Media has a positive and significant effect on student learning achievement.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a research that uses a quantitative causality design to analyze the influence between exogenous variables and endogenous variables through hypothesis testing. This study examines the effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables. Data analysis has been collected using Partial Least Square (PLS) quantitative analysis to build a conclusion on the hypothesis proposed in the study. The sample in this study were 55 students of the Management Department, Faculty of Economics and Business at Warmadewa University in semester VI. This study uses a probability random sampling of 10%. With probability sampling, the sampling is random or random from the existing population. This method is done if the members of the population are considered homogeneous. The research concept framework is as shown in the picture.

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Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

All variables in this study were measured on a Likert scale of 1-5 points. Learning motivation is encouragement that moves, directs, and maintains student behavior in learning activities, which arise from within or from outside the student, which is reflected in the need, effort and perseverance to achieve the best possible learning outcomes. The indicators of learning motivation in this study are: a) Motivation to learn because of curiosity, b) Encouragement to learn because they want to excel, c) Encouragement to learn because they want to get scholarships, d) Encouragement to learn because they want to please their parents. Media online learning line is a learning tool or intermediary that is carried out not face to face, but uses a platform that can help the teaching and learning process that is carried out even though it is far away. The online learning media in this study is e learning whose indicators are: a) The use of e-learning makes it easier to understand the material presented, b) It is required to be more creative in the use of e-learning, c) Be more enthusiastic in participating in the learning process with e-learning media, d) Lecture materials uploaded on e-learning Learning is easy to remember because it can be repeated. Student learning achievement is a real skill in a certain subject after experiencing the learning process within a certain period of time whose indicators are expressed in terms of the cumulative achievement index. The indicators of student work achievement in this study are: a) Conformity of achievement with existing assessments compared to the class average, b) Conformity of learning achievement with cumulative achievement index, c) Conformity of UTS and UAS achievements with learning efforts, d) Conformity of individual task achievement with the effort expended, e) Conformity of group task achievement with the contribution given, f) Conformity of achievement of activity in class during presentations.

The data analysis method chosen to answer the purpose of this research is to use the PLS method which has its own reliability, which is more flexible, can be used on models with small sample size data, reflective and formative indicators (Hair, et al. 2014), and is able to analyze the model. With large complexity (100-1000 indicators), Ghazali, (2011). The PLS analysis stage consists of three stages, namely: the measurement model evaluation stage (outer model), the structural model evaluation (inner model) and the significance test stage (Latan & Ghazali, 2012).

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

KaThe characteristics of the respondents in this study indicate that 63.64% of respondents are women and 72.36% are aged 18-21 years. Based on data analysis using SmartPLS 3.0 software, it can be described as follows:

Evaluation of the Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Table 1. Outer Loading Value Estimated After Execution

Variable	Indicator	Correlation Value
Motivation to learn	MB1.2	0.842
	MB1.3	0.830
	MB1.4	0.877
Online media	MO2.1	0.838
	MO2.2	0.741
	MO2.3	0.745
	MO2.4	0.915
Learning achievement	PB1.2	0.823
	PB1.3	0.790
	PB1.5	0.777

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The calculation of the outer loading value in Table 1 shows that all indicators have met the valid requirements based on the discriminant validity criteria, namely the outer loading value > 0.60 and statistically significant.

Discriminationlater Validity

Table 2. Discriminant Validity Test

Variable	AVE	$\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$	Motivation to learn	Online media
Motivation to learn	0.722	0.850		
Online media	0.661	0.813	0.156	
Learning achievement	0.635	0.797	0.537	0.347

Table 2 show that the AVE value of all constructs > 0.50 and the value of The AVE of each construct ranges from 0.797 to 0.850, which is greater than the correlation value which is between 0.156 to 0.537. so that it meets the valid requirements based on the discriminant validity criteria

Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha

Table 3. Composite Reliability Test and Cronbach Alpha

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Motivation to learn	0.810	0.886
Online media	0.828	0.886
Learning achievement	0.717	0.839

Table 3 shows that the value of composite reliability and Cronbach Alpha of each construct has been show the value is greater than 0.60 so that it meets the reliable requirements based on the composite reliability criteria.

Evaluation of the Structural Model (Structural Model/Inner Model)

Evaluation of Structural Models through R-Square (R²)

Table 4. Evaluation of the Inner Structural Model

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Learning achievement	0.359	0.334

Table 4 shows that the R² value of learning achievement is 0.359 based on Chin's criteria (Ghozali, 2011), then the model includes the criteria of a weak model, meaning that variations in learning motivation and online media by 35.9% can affect learning achievement.

Evaluation of Structural Models Through f-Square

Table 5. Evaluation of the Inner Structural Model through f-Square

Variable	Learning achievement
Motivation to learn	0.372
Online media	0.110

Based on table 5 shows that the variables of learning motivation and online media f Square values of 0.372 and 0.110, respectively, have a small effect on learning achievement.

Hypothesis testing results

Table 6. Path Analysis and Statistical Testing

	Coefficient	T Statistics	P Values	Information
Learning Motivation -> Learning Achievement	0.495	5,820	0.000	significant
Online Media -> Learning Achievement	0.269	2.033	0.043	significant

Discussion. Based on the data from the hypothesis test results, it can be explained as follows:

- 1) Influence learning motivation on student achievement

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Provide information that learning motivation has a positive effect of 0.495 on learning achievement and the relationship is significant at the 0.05 level with the t-statistical value of 5.820 which is greater than the t-table value of 1.96. This test shows that Hypothesis 1 (H1) is accepted. This states that the higher the motivation, the learning achievement will increase. Theory Planned Behavior or TPB (Theory of Planned Behavior) by Ajzen (1991) is a theory about the relationship between belief and behavior. This theory states that attitudes towards behavior, subjective norms, and perceptions of behavioral control, together form an individual's behavioral intentions. This theory underlies student behavior for achievement. Learning achievement will arise if there is motivational support in accordance with David C. McClelland's Achievement Motivation Theory. Students as individuals have a need for achievement (Need for Achievement = nAch). This result is supported by Wijaya's research (2018) which shows that the results of student learning motivation have a significant positive effect on student achievement.

2) Influence online media on student learning achievement

Give information that online media has a positive effect of 0.269 on learning achievement and the relationship is significant at the 0.05 level, where the t-statistic value of 2.033 is greater than 1.96. This test shows that Hypothesis 2(H2) is accepted. This states that the better the online learning media, the learning achievement will increase. The results of this study are not supported by research by Setyoningrum et al (2021). stated that face-to-face student learning outcomes were higher than students' mathematics learning outcomes using online learning media google classroom.

V. CONCLUSION, LIMITATIONS AND SUGESTIONS

The results of the study indicate that learning achievement can be influenced by variations in learning motivation and online learning media. This means that increasing learning motivation and online learning media can immediately improve student learning achievement.

The results of this study support the theoretical study which states that high learning motivation will be able to improve student learning achievement. Motivation causes a person to act actively to achieve high performance. This is what underlies that this research needs to be done for all Warmadewa University students as respondents. Good online learning media has a positive and significant effect on student learning achievement. E learning at Warmadewa University needs to be connected so that when online it can run smoothly.

For leaders of the Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Warmadewa, if they want to improve student achievement, they should pay attention to increasing motivation and online learning media. It is necessary to extract in-depth information about learning motivation, especially motivation to learn because the curiosity factor increases the suitability of learning achievement in attending lectures at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Warmadewa University. The plan for the following stages is that this research should be carried out periodically and continuously, meaning that after making improvements as proposed, do re-research to find out how far the effectiveness of the improvements that have been made and what can be done again.

Other researchers should develop other variables outside the model in this study and increase the range of research from other faculties at Warmadewa University and be equipped with a qualitative approach in order to obtain a more comprehensive picture of the teaching and learning process at Warmadewa University.

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